

Possible Psychopharmacological Agents. Part—XIII : Synthesis and CNS Activity of Some New Fluorine Containing 1,2,4-Triazine Derivatives

KRISHNA C. JOSHI, KALPANA DUBBY and ANSHU DANDIA

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 19 August 1982, accepted 10 March 1983

CNS activity of some new fluorinated phenylglyoxals and 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines has been evaluated and the compounds are found to be CNS depressants. In addition, a number of new fluorine containing 3-substituted-5-(fluorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazine derivatives of pharmacological interest have been synthesized by the treatment of 3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines with appropriate dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride, fluorophenacyl chloride and halogenated acids. These compounds have also been screened for preliminary CNS activity and one of them is found to act as a stimulant and to induce convulsions while the rest are CNS depressants. All synthesized compounds have been characterized by their m.p.s, elemental analyses, tlc, ir and ^1H nmr.

SCANTY information is available in literature concerning the chemistry and pharmacology of fluorine containing phenylglyoxals. In view of this, a number of new fluorine containing phenylglyoxals have been recently reported by us. Further, condensation of phenylglyoxals with thiosemicarbazide results in the formation of corresponding thiosemicarbazones which were cyclized *in situ* to yield 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines. Non-fluorinated analogs of latter compounds have aroused great interest in recent years, as the nucleus is associated with antihypertensive¹, antiinflammatory², analgesic³, cytostatic⁴ and anticancer⁵ activities. In view of such observations, these compounds have been screened for CNS activity and found to be CNS depressants. Further, a perusal of literature reveals that various activities of 1,2,4-triazines vary with substitution at 3-position⁶⁻¹⁰ and 3-dialkylamino ethylthio-group modifies CNS activity in various ways¹¹; 3-(phenacylthio) and 3-acid substituted-triazines also display biological activities¹². We have, therefore, further undertaken the synthesis of 3-dialkylaminoethylthio-1,2,4-triazines, 3-(fluorophenacylthio)-1,2,4-triazines and 3-acid substituted triazines as possible CNS agents (Scheme 1).

Experimental

Melting points of all synthesized compounds are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, model-557 spectrometer in KBr pellets. PMR (60MHz) spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer, model RB-12 spectrometer with TMS as internal standard.

Fluorinated acetophenones (Ia-d): These compounds were synthesized by adopting the method of Buu Hoi *et al*¹³, by treating appropriate fluorinated benzene with acetyl chloride in presence of

anhydrous aluminium chloride in dry carbon disulphide.

Fluorinated phenylglyoxals (IIa-e): These were prepared by the oxidation of fluorinated acetophenones with SeO_2 , as reported by us earlier¹⁴. The compounds were purified by distillation under reduced pressure and converted into hydrate forms for evaluation of CNS activity.

5-(Fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines (IIIa-e): The glyoxals were treated with thiosemicarbazide to give corresponding thiosemicarbazones, which were cyclized *in situ* to yield 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines¹⁴.

5-(Fluorophenyl)-3-(dialkylaminoethylthio)-1,2,4-triazines (IVa-g): An aqueous solution of appropriate dialkylaminoethylchloride hydrochloride (0.015 M) was added to a stirred mixture of appropriate 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazine (0.01 M) in 1.0 N sodium hydroxide (10 ml) over a period of 5 min. The reaction mixture was further stirred for 1 hr and left overnight. It was diluted with water, acidified and filtered. The filtrate, on basification, afforded the crude precipitate, which was filtered and purified by recrystallization and gave single spot on tlc (Table 1).

5-(Fluorophenyl)-3-(4-fluorophenacylthio)-1,2,4-triazines (Va-b): A mixture of 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazine (0.01 M) and 4-fluorophenacylchloride (0.01 M) in absolute ethanol (60 ml) was heated under reflux for 8 hr. The crystals obtained on cooling were filtered and recrystallized from ethanol yielding the desired compound.

5-(4-Fluorophenyl)-1,2,4-triazino-3-thiolacids (VI and VII): A mixture of 5-(fluorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazine (0.01 M), halogenated acid (0.01 M) and fused sodium acetate (0.01 M) in dry ethanol was heated under reflux for 10 hr. The

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF 3,5-DISUBSTITUTED 1,2,4-TRIAZINES

Compound No.	R ¹	R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	Solvent for crystallization	%N Found (Calcd.)
IVa	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	114	78	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ FN ₄ OS	Pet. ether	17.59 (17.50)
IVb	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	78	77	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ FN ₄ S	Benzene	17.70 (17.61)
IVc	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	79	75	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ FN ₄ S	Pet. ether	18.29 (18.42)
IVd	3,4-F ₂ , C ₆ H ₃	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	80	71	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ F ₂ N ₄ OS	Pet. ether	16.53 (16.56)
IVe	3,4-F ₂ , C ₆ H ₃	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	78	74	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ F ₂ N ₄ S	Pet. ether	16.59 (16.66)
IVf	3-Cl, 4-F, C ₆ H ₃	SCH ₂ -N	118	71	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ ClFN ₄ S	Methanol	16.32 (16.37)
IVg	C ₆ F ₅	SCH ₂ CH ₂ -N	160	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ F ₅ N ₄ OS	Methanol	14.17 (14.28)
Va	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	SCH ₂ COC ₂ H ₄ .F(p)	220	80	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ F ₂ N ₄ OS	Ethanol	12.19 (12.24)
Vb	2-CH ₃ , 4-F, C ₆ H ₃	SCH ₂ COC ₂ H ₄ .F(p)	197	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₉ F ₂ N ₄ OS	Ethyl acetate	11.72 (11.76)
VI	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	SCH ₂ COOH	158	69	C ₁₁ H ₉ FN ₄ O ₂ S	Benzene	15.79 (15.84)
VII	4-F, C ₆ H ₄	S.C ₆ H ₄ .COOH	227	71	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ FN ₄ O ₂ S	Ethanol	12.78 (12.84)

TABLE 2—CNS SCREENING DATA OF FLUORINE CONTAINING PHENYLGLYOXALS AND 3-MERCAPTO-1,2,4-TRIAZINES

Comp. No.	Dose (mg/kg) i.p.	1	2	3a	3b	4	5	6	7	8a	8b	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
IIa	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	nil		
	1000	↓↓	↓↓	↓↓	↓↓	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	-	100	681	↓.2
	186.2	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	nil		
IIb	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	25		
	1000	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	++	-	75	681	↓.2
	215	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	nil		
IIIa	186.2	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	nil		
	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	++	++	+	++	++	++	+	+	++	-	100		
	215	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	+	++	++	++	+	+	++	-	50	215	↓.3
IIIb	100	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	nil		
	43	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-	nil		
	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	+	++	++	++	+	+	++	-	100		
IIIc	215	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	-	+	++	++	+	+	++	-	nil	316	↓.3
	63.2	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	nil		
	464	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	nil		
IIId	1000	↓	↓	↓	↓	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	++	-	25	825	↓.3
	165	↓	↓	↓	↓	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	nil		

Abbreviations: ↑ ↓ = increase or decrease in reactivity. - = no effect, + = mild effect.

1. S.M.A., 2. Respiration, 3. Reactivity (a) sound (b) touch, 4. Writhing, 5. Ataxia, 6. Tremors, 7. Pinnal and corneal reflex, 8. Posture and Tone (a) body (b) limb, 9. Catalepsy, 10. Ptosis, 11. Loss of Righting reflex, 12. Inclined plane test, 13. Mortality % (24 hr), 14. ALD₅₀(mg/kg), 15. body temp. (°C).

reaction mixture was cooled to room temp. and the solid thus separated, was recrystallized from ethanol.

The characteristic and analytical data are recorded in Table 1.

Evaluation of CNS activity:

A number of phenylglyoxals (IIa and IIb), 3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazines (IIIa, IIIb and IIIc) and 3-

substituted-triazines (IVa, IVb, IVc, IVe, Va and VI; Scheme 1) have been screened for CNS activity. Solutions of the compounds were prepared as gum acacia suspensions and subsequent dilutions were made with distilled water. The tested animals were adult albino mice. All tested compounds were administered intraperitoneally. The effects were observed at the time of peak effect of the compound

Scheme 1

concerned. The results are summarized in Table 2. The following types of activities were observed in case of phenylglyoxals and 3-mercapto triazines. However, 3-substituted triazines were observed only for behavioural and analgesic activity.

(A) *Behavioural activity*: The animals were observed for 3 hr after drug administration by the method of Horn *et al.*¹⁵ for any evidence of CNS stimulation, depression or any other autonomic effects.

(B) *Analgesic activity*: This was tested by tail pinch method¹⁶.

(C) *Anticonvulsant activity*: The procedure described by Swinyard¹⁷ was employed for determination of anticonvulsant activity.

(D) *Antireserpine activity*: The activity was tested according to procedure described by Rubin¹⁸.

(E) *Acute toxicity*: This was evaluated according to the method of Turner¹⁹.

Results and Discussion

Spectral studies (ir and pmr): 3-Mercapto-1,2,4-triazines exist in thione form in solid state and show strong absorption bands in the region of 3200-3400 cm^{-1} (N-H stretching). When these compounds were treated with different dialkylaminoethyl chlorides, phenacyl chloride and halogenated acids, the >N-H absorption band disappeared providing a strong support for formation of S-substituted compounds. In compounds IV and V,

characteristic $-\text{CH}_2-$ stretching bands at 2800 and 2900 cm^{-1} are also present. A characteristic sharp band at 1670 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$) is present in compound V. Compounds VI and VII show a sharp band at 1710 cm^{-1} ($>\text{C}=\text{O}$, acidic) and a broad band in the region of 3300-3500 cm^{-1} ($-\text{OH}$). All these compounds showed $>\text{C}=\text{F}$ absorptions at 1130-1300 cm^{-1} .

In pmr spectra, all compounds showed disappearance of mercapto proton signal at δ 3.4-3.6 ppm besides some sharp signals in the region of δ 9.1 ($\text{HC}=\text{N}-$, methine proton characteristic of triazine system), 3.35-3.40 ($-\text{S}-\text{CH}_2$) and 7.1-8.8 ppm (aromatic protons). PMR spectra of compounds IVa-g also showed resonance signals between δ 2.4-2.8 ppm (broad due to $\text{N}-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2$) and δ 1.5-1.8 ppm (CH_3-CH_2). In pmr spectra of compounds V and VI, the $-\text{SCH}_2$ signal is shifted downfield at δ 4.32 and 3.95 ppm due to the presence of highly electron withdrawing groups on either side.

CNS activity: At different dose levels of compounds as indicated in Table 2, SMA, respiration and reactivity towards sound and touch decreases; writhing, ataxia, muscle tone of body and limbs, loss of righting, pinnal and corneal reflexes have also been observed in some compounds indicating that compounds IIIa and IIIb may be active as neuroleptics.

Mercapto triazines IIIa, IIIb and IIIc show considerable decrease in spontaneous motor activity (60, 50, 40%, respectively) indicating CNS depressant action. Compounds IIIa and IIIb were thus found to be CNS depressants. Phenylglyoxals are slightly toxic but acute toxicity of compounds IIIa and IIIb is high as revealed by low value of ALD_{50} . Toxicity decreases by replacement of fluorine of phenyl group of 1,2,4-triazines with decrease in depressant action as in the case of IIIc.

All phenylglyoxals and 3-mercaptotriazines were found to be sensitive towards noxious stimuli, failed to afford protection against electric shock and failed to antagonise ptosis, crouching and diarrhoea in tests for analgesic, anticonvulsant and antireserpine activity.

CNS screening of 3-substituted 1,2,4-triazines indicate that all compounds except IVc produce a diminution in the locomotor activity and decreases general awareness within 5 min after injection of compounds. SMA, respiration and reactivity towards sound and touch decreases, writhing is present and the animals become less active. Mortality was nil within 24 hr in all cases. All these effects show depressant action but this action decreases with replacement of mercapto group with secondary amino group and toxicity is also decreased.

Substitution of morpholino ring showed depressant effect equal to that of 3-mercapto triazine without any toxicity, and piperidino substituted triazines showed less depressant action. With compound IVc there was immediate appearance of

muscular twitching and tachyphoea and generalized convulsions, both tonic and clonic, appeared within 15 min, convulsions ceased after 1.5 to 2 hr when there was generalized flaccidity.

Thus, 1,2,4-triazines with pyrrolidine substituent showed stimulant action and induced convulsion and can be used as chemical convulsants analogous to pentylenetetrazole induced convulsions.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. B. N. Dhawan, Deputy Director, Division of Pharmacology, C.D.R.I., Lucknow and Dr. J. N. Sinha, Department of Pharmacology, K. G. Medical College, Lucknow for pharmacological screening of the compounds. One of the authors (A. D.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for financial assistance.

References

1. W. P. HEILMAN, R. D. HEILMAN, A. JAMES, R. J. WAYNER, J. M. GULLO and J. S. ARIYAN, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1979, **22**, 671.
2. J. M. GULLO, W. P. HEILMAN, R. J. WAYNER and R. E. MOSSER, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 821, 381, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1979, **90**, 121664m.
3. G. VITET, H. COUSE and G. MOUZIN, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 810, 052, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 197609x.
4. C. CRISTESCU and M. LAZARESCU, *Rev. Roum. Chim.*, 1969, **14**, 797; *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, **71**, 112890n.
5. F. SORM, A. ZAKUBONIC and L. SLRCHTA, *Experientia*, 1960, **12**, 271.
6. W. B. LACEFIELD, *Fr. Demande*, 2, 343, 479, 1977; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 24872m.
7. R. R. SCHMIDT, W. PARKER, L. EUE and H. TIMMLER, *Pestic Sci.*, 1975, **6**, 239; *Chem. Abs.*, 1976, **84**, 85432z.
8. W. B. LACEFIELD and P. K. HO, *Belg. Pat.*, 839, 496, 1976; *Chem. Abs.*, 1977, **87**, 68431t.
9. A. J. SCHEUSTER, JR., J. C. MARTIN, D. M. SPARTZ and P. J. WIDNER, *Ger. Offen.*, 2, 800, 385, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 180055r.
10. Lilly Eli and Co., *Austrian Patent*, 341, 534, 1978; *Chem. Abs.*, 1978, **89**, 24369r.
11. R. MONTGAZZA, R. TOMENASINI, R. FUSCO and S. ROSSI, *Arch. Intern. Pharmacodynamic.*, 1953, **95**, 123; *Chem. Abs.*, 1954, **48**, 3348d.
12. A. K. MANSOUR, S. B. AWAD, S. ANTOUR, *Z. Naturforsch. Teil B.*, 1974, **29**, 792; *Chem. Abs.*, 1975, **82**, 10034z.
13. N. P. BUU HOI, N. G. HOEN and P. JACQUIGNON, *Rec. Trav. Chim.*, 1949, **68**, 781; *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, **44**, 2509g.
14. K. C. JOSHI, K. DUBRY and A. DANDIA, *Heterocycles*, 1981, **16**, 1545.
15. H. J. HORN, *Biometrics*, 1956, **12**, 311.
16. C. BIANCHI and J. FRANCESCHINI, *Brit. J. Pharmacol. Chemotherap.*, 1954, **9**, 280.
17. E. SWINYARD, "Laboratory Assay of Clinically Effective Antileptic Drugs", *J. Am. Pharm. Ass. Sci. Ed.*, 1949, **38**, 201.
18. B. RUBIN, M. H. MALONA, H. WAVAIR and J. C. BURK, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1957, **25**, 120.
19. R. A. TURNER, "Screening Methods in Pharmacology", Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 72.